

Knowledge and Different Levels of Reality

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1. Introduction

Usually science talks about a world that contradicts our common sense or our natural interpretations: Earth's decentralization inverts our relation with stars, objects lose their dimension of solidity to be crushed in energy fields, living beings are not traced back to a repetitive genealogy but to a changing one, the dimensional ellipsis allowed by mathematics annihilates the ternary basis of experience, time itself seems to rest on a space. How did we get to this point and why? How does the reality in which we live (and that science deconstructs in a counter-intuitive way) emerge¹? What is its meaning? Do real and apparent predicates, as Galileo wanted, exist or do we have primary and secondary qualities as suggested by Locke?

In order to discuss epistemology, it is fundamental to know the epistemic apparatus of the human being in its basic coordinates, so as to investigate the stability of knowledge, which today seems to be anything but stable. Every event, in order to be understood, needs

¹ Wolpert L. (1992), *The Unnatural Nature of Science*, Cambridge – London, Harvard University Press.

to be transformed in its kinetic dimension, but the evaluation of the movement requires a still background, as it depends on a premise of stability. Therefore, the epistemological foundations are the prerequisites to grasp an event, they represent its *cliché*. Thus, should we be pleased with an instrumental view of epistemology? The world appears to us as a group of predicates that we acquire through our sense organs: the texture of a piece of furniture, the taste of a strawberry, the colour of a flower, the smell of mowed grass. It seems like that, but we know that the perception of predicates does not belong exclusively to the object – for example not everyone agrees on the predicates of a particular event and different species always notice different predicates when exposed to the same phenomenon. On the other hand a predicate is not an invention of the organs through which we interact with reality, if it is true that it is possible to easily dwell in the world thanks to the semiology of the predicates, obtaining confirmations to our needs. Moreover we experience both synchronic and diachronic relationships between predicates; we can infer norms that, even while not being necessarily stable, can give us a good forecasting probability. Often acquired correlations offer us the possibility to favour and foresee the occurrence of a phenomenon. If predicates are neither exclusively of the world nor the result of a pure invention of our sense organs we can say, with approximation, that they are the rising outcome of the interaction between our peculiarities – how we face the world – and some general and specific qualities of the real. Therefore, this emergence, our way of “seeing” reality, is

not an expression of the world in itself, but of our particular dialogue with the world.

Why do we dialogue with the world? For a very simple reason: in order to live we need answers, we need to interiorise order so as to stabilise our own improbability. Living beings are thermodynamically unstable systems, a dissipative structure – to put it in Prigogine's words² – whose temporary resistance in the complexity of the general non-equilibrium is due to their opening, to their interaction with the world. The comings and goings through a cell membrane, that of an intestine or of woody foliage, or that of blood vascularization are an emergence of the world, whose dialogue is capable of delimiting an environment, a domain of metabolic validity, through the edges of the interchange.

Living beings are not autarchic: they need to dialogue if they want to preserve the internal order that characterizes them and information is the most precious resource to this purpose. On the other side, information is not in the world, it is not an objective reality, whether obvious or cryptic, or simply accessible. Information lies in the *dialogue* with the world, in the point where a particular question intersects a field of possibility. The answers do not come from our exposure to the world, as this would mean that the answers are in the world. They do not emerge from projective or creative construction either, as this would mean that the answers are simply ours. The answers are the result of a precise

² Kondepudi D., Prigogine I. (1998), *Modern Thermodynamics. From Heat Engines to Dissipative Structures*, New York, Wiley.

question, they are a reassembly of the worlds around a flow of key words. Therefore, the dialogue has an ecosystemical structure: there the living dwells, there it finds its real nourishment, that is, information. On the other hand, information is not something released from the operative content of the inquiring being; in other worlds, there is always need of a scale or a gradient of information for the circumstantial and causal correlates required to emerge. The operative space of the epistemic entity represents the fitness of the inquirer, whose fortune does not depend on a generic or absolute presentation of the real, but on a precise catalogue of risks and opportunities. In other words, the inquirer lives at a precise level of reality, given by a specific organization of the real, where the organization itself produces binding effects and emergences, which are qualities that cannot be subsumed from other organizational fields. Therefore, common sense is a way to live reality. It is neither a projection or an invention, nor is it the only possible reality.

2. Questioning the World to Obtain Fitness

Charles Darwin showed us that reproductive success is the key to understanding the shape,³ the *hic et nunc* of the *natura naturata*, because only

³ Darwin C. [1859] (2003), *On the Origin of the Species by Means of Natural Selection, Or, The Preservation of Favoured Races in the Struggle for Life*, Peterborough, Broadview Press.

those who are able to replicate themselves with success are now here to show off their characteristics. However, reproductive success, able to gain a perfect coherence between shape and function, an organism and its environment, ecological niche and behavioural traits, anatomy and physiology – a coherence that, first of all, is congruity and adherence to a style, an equilibrium between needs of efficacy and efficiency – has precise requests for the world. Acquired information allows for the maintenance of an internal order of the living: this negentropy is existence, an expression of a *here and now*, replication and evolution.

Can the energy of which a living being feeds on be reduced to an epistemic function? The questions deal with the events that cross the specific order of that given living being, and therefore they ask for basic epistemic correlates, that is, a totally peculiar dialogue with the world. Thus, we can consider the epistemic apparatus of a species as a field of stability that allows us to capture only the events of the world that are important under the profile of fitness. It is the field of dialogue that defines the epistemic apparatus. Therefore, its partiality should not be surprising for us – the field of dialogue reflects the subjectivity of the question, the specific election of the events to record, the type of information that we are looking for – but this does not justify falls into epistemic relativism, which is the total disarticulation of the functional result of the consistency of the world. If in an elongative phenomenon we are prone to read the entity which is in movement in respect to the background –

and so we say that it is the lion that comes closer and not the savannah that moves back – that preconceived interpretation is not entirely true; hence the illusion that the moon moves in the sky and not the clouds, as Eibl Eibesfeldt said.⁴ Still, in the context where we dwell, it is highly probable and moreover it has an adaptive meaning which is not indifferent.

The epistemic apparatus calibrated by natural selection does not follow a necessity of an *absolute* knowledge of reality, but of species-specific action towards reality on the basis of strongly characterized exigencies. Therefore, the epistemic apparatus does not reflect reality but the need and the checkmate position established to obtain the breeding success of the subject. Nevertheless, the epistemic apparatus is calibrated on the resistance of the real. As the wings of a bird reflect upward currents, the fins and the shape of a fish are the mirror of fluids viscosity, while the gills witness the presence of dissolved oxygen in the water. In this way the epistemic apparatuses are the result of the peculiar needs of adaptation of a species in its interaction with the external reality.

Therefore, epistemic apparatuses are not simple ways of access to the real that, like glasses, owe their functionality to their transparency and to their capacity of objectively reflecting reality. They are rather instruments that act on the world, as a wing does with a particular function correlated to

⁴ Eibl Eibesfeldt I. (1971) *Love and Hate: On the Natural History of Basic Behaviour Patterns*, Munich, Piper & Co.

the substrate it has to deal with. However, even if compared to a particular predicate of resistance – not all the resistances of the real act as selectors – the epistemic apparatus reflects the damages made by processes of negation or constraints given by reality. Thus the epistemic apparatuses follow the needs of selection: *a*) the particular needs of information which can be referred to *that* living being, in his dwelling within a well structured “living environment” – inhabiting rainforest trees has different informative urgencies compared to moving in the open space of the savannah – and “lifestyle” (to be an alert predator is different from feeding on fruits and berries); *b*) the consistency of the counterpart that the subject needs to face up. The world the subject dwells in has relevance because it is made of discrete and solid entities and not because it is built of energy fields. That world is characterized by “common norms” – such as gravity, the surface-volume relationship, the common movement of parts – therefore, it is probable that more species face it with the same epistemic strategies. Yet, that world consist of a “plurality of dialogic fields”, so that reality is more like a field of virtuality to be realized rather than an object to be approached.

Thus, it is necessary to recognize not the fallacy of the senses, but the meaning of the phylogenetic dialogue. The processes of cutting, connecting, attributing, ordering and asking, which constitute the occurrence of a phenomenon and its exit from the realm of the virtual, need to be traced back to that adaptive ontics that is established on the partiality of reality. Both the sensory access (the

phenomenal virtuality) and the intersection with the event (the actualization of the phenomenon) can lay on a contextual pillow, so to speak, insofar as they partialize reality. If we think in a creationistic way, we will inevitably tend to discern the *how* from the *what* of knowing, falling in the inevitable dichotomy between inductive and deductive regimes and in its aporetic deviation.

In my opinion, this dualism is the result of an anthropocentric reading of the epistemic approach and the heritage of a not yet accepted evolutionist vision of the cognitive process. On the other side, if we recognize in knowing not only the partiality of the intersection with the real, which derives from the phylogenetic specialization, but also the internalization of predicates themselves (which are responsible for that partiality, exactly as gills reflect the hydric environment of a fish), we will realize that the “how of knowing” is the result of a previous internalization, even though it is not realized through an evolutionary individual process of the “what” of knowing. Therefore, knowing implies an epistemic apparatus “able to” or “called to” make the context of the living being’s life partial or usable – this happens if it’s clear that: *a*) it is impossible to interact with the world if we are lacking questions and theories; *b*) the emerging interaction leads, in turn, to questions and theories of a different order. The how and the object of knowledge are only apparently two separate realities, because each individual that is called to the epistemic act, in his first intersection with the world, is already provided with an inherited phylogenetic apparatus, a

how that results from a previous selective exposition to the context, which is the object of knowing, in its predicates of resistance and influence.

Thus, the world of knowing has already interiorized some predicates of the object, those implicated in the adaptive process, so that the how reflects the thing. However, it reflects the thing not in its being as-it-is, but in its influential predicates under the adaptive profile, inevitably building a phenomenal partiality. Therefore, the how is an a-priori thing, redefined on the basis of the adaptive meaning of some of its predicates, exactly as respiration only captures the oxygen component of the air. Thus, the first organizational dimension of the epistemic apparatus can be traced back to phylogenesis: to a process of partial or distorted configuration of knowing. Therefore the how of knowing is not an a-priori that transcends the object of knowing, but the result of a selective dialectic between the object itself and the ontic style of the knower, a process that improves the capacity of partializing a thing on the basis of relevant predicates, interiorizing the predicates as a key to the corresponding keyhole. So the epistemic apparatus is the result of a dialectical function that intersects the objective of the *taxon* in phylogenetics and the resistances-influences that are virtually present in the context, displayed in precise predicates. Ultimately the epistemic apparatus is a solving organ, called to solve the problematic contents that the subjects of a certain species will face in their lives.

3. Levels of Reality as an Organization of the Real

Therefore, dialogue is a way to organize reality, and epistemology is the positioning on a level of reality in order to get useful information. This means that it is not an approximation but an emergence, a construction that is not arbitrary or paradigmatic, a way to eliminate the background noise and make specific contents emerge. Mental categories and sense organs are cabled together to organize a level of reality that is consistent under an adaptive profile, meaning that it needs to sustain that particular species in its enduring desire to keep a highly improbable internal organization. The order, or better, the predictability of a description-explication depends on the scale of observation, which is the level on which our epistemic apparatuses lay on. As Zbilut and Giuliani already wrote “The universe can be seen as a painting with different relative levels of apparent determinism and noise depending on the scale of observation”.⁵ Basically, that scale-dependence tells us that by modifying our access, for example through a technological apparatus, placing ourselves at a different level of reality, we will be facing a different organization of reality and this will require us to modify the descriptive-explicative structure.

⁵ Giuliani A., Zbilut J. P. (2009), *L'ordine della complessità*, Milan, Jaca Book, p. 72.

To organize reality does not mean to make it up, but to extract some scale emergences from a “field of definite and resistant possibilities”. In this sense, I regard Maurizio Ferraris’ concept of the “resistance of the real”⁶ as particularly adequate. Moreover, this makes us understand an important epistemological principle: that is, the fact that there are many ways to read reality, but only one way through which the real falsifies our assertions. This means that the instrument is not an amplification of the phylogenetic endowment but a transformation, which is capable of modifying the scale of access and, in turn, the gradient of determinism and noise that we encounter as well as the type of information we can obtain. Additionally this means that:

1) even though the real exists, there is no privileged level of reality capable of containing the others;

2) it is not possible to simultaneously access various levels of reality;

3) the human being is not allowed to reduce reality to a formal scheme.

I agree with Hilary Putnam and his “common sense realism”, in claiming that what exist is independent from its knowability and that there can be many correct descriptions of reality.⁷ On the other side, if reality is organized under binding structures,

⁶ Ferraris M. (2012), “Esistere è resistere”, in M. De Caro, M. Ferraris (edited by), *Bentornata realtà. Il nuovo realismo in discussione*, Turin, Einaudi, pp. 139-165.

⁷ Putnam H. (1992), *Renewing Philosophy*, Cambridge, Harvard University Press, p. 9.

each endowed with particular resistances, the impossibility of arriving to a unique and objective knowledge of the real is evident: it is only possible to increase the informative space. These diverse organizations of the real, each incomplete from an explanatory point of view if analysed at the level of components – to refer to Terrence Deacon’s hypothesis – can be defined as “levels of reality”.⁸

Each level of reality cannot be explained but through its own centrifugation: hence the explicative non-self-sufficiency of any epistemic level. The organization which a level of reality comes from depends on the potentiality of the real and on the type of interrogation that is predisposed. In that sense, in order to find an absolute conception of the real we could define it not as a specific status but as a space of virtuality inside which different levels of reality are admissible. The level of reality brings to light some phenomenal predicates, which do not need to be regarded as projective entities even though they are emergent ones.

Therefore, epistemology is not “making up a context”, but a particular intersection with reality that happens on the basis of a temporary dwelling in reality. In order to act on a particular context it is necessary to define some gradients of correlation and therefore emphasise some aspects over others. Assuming a positional scale, a new order emerges. This order is not arbitrary or in-

⁸ Deacon T. W. (2001), *Incomplete Nature: How Mind Emerged from Matter*, New York, Norton & Company.

vented and nevertheless it does not depend on the order of magnitude on which the observation-dwelling is positioned. This hunger for well-defined answers makes a dialogue or an informative exchange emerge, electing a specific field of interface that actualizes one among the multiple possibilities of reality, forming an organization inside the field of expressiveness. The subject is located in the dimension of a species and an individual because of this positioning of the interface, which allows him or her to observe exclusively the events that have some relevance to his or her problem.

On the other hand, it is wrong to believe that only the experiential level or the one of direct observation – common sense, that is, phylogenetic epistemology – has a right to define reality, as is often supported by common sense realists. A scientific theory has the same right over direct experience in the description of reality, the same possibility of making predicates emerge that tell us something more regarding the field of virtuality of the real, the same right to face the fields of resistance of the real. Moving away from phylogenetic epistemology, through anthropodecentrative mechanisms – and the counter-intuitive character of the science talks about this centrifugal process – new phenomenal predicates and new resistances of the real will emerge. Every time the questioner hybridises her hereditary endowments with an instrument (which leads to a particular kind of knowledge, and opens new existential dimensions thanks to the animal epiphany) she modifies her dialogic structure with reality. Detaching herself from

common sense, the questioner receives a diverse organization or a scale gradient, originating not a construction but a new level of reality.

The concept of level of reality reminds me of a passage of Aristotle which is referred to the theories of Speusippus who: “imagines more levels of reality starting from the One, and he imagines principles for each level of reality”.⁹ The concept of multiplicity of the principles implies a positional choice on the part of the questioner. Following that indication, in a dialogic conception of the descriptive-explicative experience, the phenomenal predicates do not depend only on the intersection between the properties of the observer and those of the observed, but they also depend on the level of reality where the observer is located.

We can synthesise what we have said so far in 3 points:

- 1) not only does the observer adhere to reality, but the observer himself was also constructed on the basis of the consistence of the real;
- 2) the level of reality depends on the level of virtuality of the real and on the characteristics of the observer;
- 3) the level of reality depends on the type of questions that the observer asks the field of virtuality of the real in a given moment.

We recognize and access a statute of reality through the partiality of its appearance, its

⁹ Cf. Berti E. (2010), *Sumphilosophein. La vita nell'accademia di Platone*, Rome, Laterza, p. 106.

giving itself to us in a certain way. Therefore, we intersect predicates of resistance or of influence with our specifying form of being, but also in this limitation of access, what we define a phenomenon or a phenomenal predicate is an organization of the real, a possible expression of the real. The truth/falsity of a statement depends on its interrogative structure, in other words it depends on how I intersect reality, on the level at which I pose the question, that is, “what I am interested in” and “how I ask the question for it”. If, for whatever reason, the interrogation does not intersect any specific resistances, these do not emerge: our epistemic apparatus is not structured to make the Copernican universe emerge because the type of interrogation that could make it emerge is not pertinent to the “epistemic positioning” of the species. It is necessary to hybridize that epistemic apparatus to make new interrogative structures emerge, which means that it is necessary to start new dialogues, and this happens every time the human being builds some anthropodecentering mechanisms.

On the other side, it is undeniable that so as to question reality it is indispensable to locate ourselves on a precise level, to establish some parameters of noise and determinism, that is, to assume a scale gradient that makes specific corresponding parts emerge. The anthropodecenterative mechanism – for example to observe the sky through binoculars – does not make a unique structure of the real emerge, but it makes new organizations emerge, helping us in making new resistances emerge and to enlarge our observa-

tional scope over reality. Therefore, theories are not approximations but specific interrogations that allow for the emergence of new resistances and thus the acquisition of more information on the real – and, therefore, the formulation of new questions. Thus, the predictability of a theory is connected to the congruence of the interrogative structure in respect to the type of phenomenon that we want to investigate, so that the level of predictability is attributable to the space of probability in which we dwell. Each interrogative structure has to intersect some resistances and not others; it depends on the type of scale positioning in which the interrogation is located, that is, the capacity of making only *some* events emerge and ordering them.

Hence, common sense is just one among the various possible organizations of the real, which is capable of giving to our phylogenetic trajectory a supporting field on which to formulate the questions that are useful to us. This means that common sense is not the “reality” but a presentation of it, that is, a level of reality – one that has intersected the inquiries of the species – but, even better, it is not a projection or an arbitrary construction and it is not an approximation. We could say that the level of reality occupied by the experience of common sense represents a little observatory on reality that has been useful-indispensable to solve the difficulties of our species-specific fitness. Therefore, even if the phenomenal predicates belong securely to the observed object, they are not constructed, since they have acted on the epistemic apparatus to adjust the “expe-

riential how". However, their phenomenal particularity emerges from the way in which we question reality, that is, from the horizon and the depth of our observatory.

4. Towards a Dialogic Epistemology

Secondly, it is necessary to see the epistemic hereditary apparatus not as a finished or "almost-finished" instrument, meaning that we forecast an already given or reachable condition of congruity or perfection, but as a multiplier of epistemic apparatuses. The EVO of the epistemic apparatus is functional to the ontogenetic DEVO, which can be seen as a generator of new structures of knowledge on the basis of a re-adjustment or transformation of past knowledge and simultaneously a re-definition of the domains of validity of past knowledge itself.¹⁰

Whilst knowing, the being bends its epistemic apparatus' new predicates and thus modifies the horizon of its intersecting-questioning the world. Thus, the here and now of the knowing subject is the dimensional result – each dimension represents the evolutionary virtual to build new fields of organization of reality – of the previous processes of phylogenetic and ontogenetic knowledge. From this we can understand that knowing entails the involvement of various dimensions of the being, which are

¹⁰ Carroll S. B. (2005), *Endless Forms Most Beautiful: The New Science of Evo Devo*, New York, Norton & Company.

diachronically recursive, leading to an explanation of the phenomenon that, in the here and now of the subject, is the result of the diverse evolutionary declinations of the epistemic apparatus in its previous cognitive acts. We can say that the interrogation – which is the structure of dialogue with the real located on a precise level – does not only give answers such as true or false, but it also retro-acts on the epistemic system by modifying it. Therefore it is not possible to know without modifying our own epistemic apparatuses. The dualism between knowing subject and known object and the unidirectionality of the act are just apparent. Thus, scientific theories are not separated or extraneous entities to the inherited phylogenetic epistemic apparatus: they derive from it, even though not directly. The hybridization with an instrument generates a new residence of the living and thus a new level of reality through which it is possible to dialogue-interrogate, but this dwelling is still rooted in common sense.

We are now beginning to understand that the dichotomy and the opposition between common sense realism and scientific realism is only apparent. A scientific theory is nothing more than an anthropodecentrative process that does not at all deny the precedence of experience but simply gives it a domain of validity. Interrogations proposed at a given level of reality produce responsive surpluses which evoke new emergences and are at the basis of the need to activate new levels of reality. Therefore, progression is given by the recurring effect, in the sense of declination, of the interrogation itself. By

the term “declination” I mean an introjection of the known object that modifies the successive “how” of knowledge. At the end, even phylogenesis, in its diverse aspects of functional correlation, is nothing more than a process of introjection of possible predicates of the real.

On the other side, reality always presents an edge of novelty to each living being – an accident in respect to the interrogative species-specific standards – so that we can talk about a “principle of singularity of the real”: each living being needs to re-configure its own epistemic apparatus. This makes us overcome the static conception of *Umwelt* proposed by von Uexküll,¹¹ non only in the monodological sense expressed by Heidegger, but in a non-evolutionary or non-closure sense within phylogenetic epistemology. The “apparatuses of conception” of the world are evolutionary entities, and inevitably every living being needs to exit from the bubble in order to face the principle of singularity. The evolution of phylogenetic epistemology interiorises the act of knowing itself, so that common sense is an entity which presents edges of stability and areas of declination. It is obvious that the transformation of these apparatuses is affected by the individual experiences of the subject – which obviously are limited – and

¹¹ Von Uexküll J. (1957), “A Stroll Through the Worlds of Animals and Men: A Picture Book of Invisible Worlds” in *Instinctive Behavior: The Development of a Modern Concept*, Claire H. Schiller (edited by), New York, International Universities Press, pp. 5–80.

by the translations that the group (population or species) interiorises into a cultural canon. In this case the information does not pass through genetic mechanisms, but through an externalization of the information inside the processes of socialization, first of all the parental process. Moreover, nowadays people discuss if the experience of the individual can, in such a way, be epigenetically interiorised also in the genetic field.

What we observe in the human being is an exaggeration of the process of externalization through instruments of sedimentation of information: rituals, costumes, writings, disciplines, just to cite some. But there is more. The human being has hybridised his own epistemic apparatus with external entities – heterospecific and instrumental – and this has amplified the evolutionary process of the apparatus of phytogenic heritage, throughout a process that is not ascribable to ontogenesis, since it is highly anthropocentric. That’s the reason why I referred to that event as ontopoiesis. The *techne* is not only a simple operative apparatus, a secondary entity that is at the service of the human, because it operates a metamorphosis of interface: first of all the *techne* is a way to start new dialogue with the world and a way to formulate new questions. As a consequence it is more correct to talk about techno-science, admitting an internal recursivity.

Through the techno-scientific activity new levels of reality emerge for the human being, who can then operate new surveys on the resistances of the reality. Basically, this is an enlargement of the horizon of informative

access, that allows him to identify a plurality of domains of validity. Using the hybridative operation permitted by techno-science, the human being makes a sort of survey on reality, investigating new levels of reality and looking for the relative resistances. If asaying a major number of resistances means to increase our knowledge of the real, it is obvious that the techno-scientific activity helps us enhance our interrogations. However, I think the physicalist claim over a privileged interface of interrogation of the real is wrong.

If it is true that the phenomenal qualities, given specific partiality of access, can transform themselves if declinative or hybridative apparatuses are used, it is also evident that only a scale operation has been realised, making new coordinates of order and noise emerge. Therefore, is there a way or a direction to follow in research? I think there is and the way, which is suggested to me from Bachelard¹² to Piaget,¹³ is that of travelling through different levels of reality, exploring in each level the resistance of the real. Thus, lifts are nothing more than hybridative processes with non-human realities, such as the *techne* that allows an anthropodecentralization from anthropocentric epistemology. How can we call this activity if not techno-science?

Knowing means hybridizing our own epistemic apparatuses. Insisting on subtract-

¹² Bachelard G. [1932] 2002, *The Formation of the Scientific Mind*. Manchester, Clinamen Press.

¹³ Piaget J. (1954), *The Construction of Reality in the Child*, New York, Routledge.

ing the *episteme* from this introjective flow is an otiose and diverted operation, in the false view that the entity that intersects the world has been created with the particular aim it has *here and now*. Along this line we would be led to believe that human epistemology has been structured with the aim of conceiving abstract theories on the universe or of dealing with the imperceptible atomic world. We arrived to formulate those theories not in a solipsistic way and remaining inside our epistemic apparatuses, but using external contributes that, as crutches, modified our access to reality.

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